

Energy-Momentum Conservation and Slit Resolution in the Two Slit Scenario

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It is sometimes asked why quantum mechanics of two slit interference does not lead to the determination of the slit through which a photon passes. To know this, we argue one must follow the photon in time and so have high time resolution.. We argue that the time associated with motion over a wavelength (which is roughly the length between slits) is of higher resolution than \hbar/E , but it is the latter which governs time resolution. Thus, according to quantum mechanics, one cannot resolve the time linked with motion through one slit or another.

This begs the question: Why should there be time and spatial resolution for a free particle? We have argued in (1) that this is due to conservation of energy and momentum for t and x respectively. Conservation of a variable is not simply associated with one variable, but with at least two. For example, conservation of energy means that E at t_1 is the same as E at t_2 and for momentum, p at x_1 is the same as p at x_2 . In classical mechanics, it is assumed one has infinite t and x resolution, but conservation of energy and momentum must be put in by hand. The question is: What is it put in by hand in nature? If one uses a probabilistic description, then there should be zero probability for events which do not conserve energy or momentum. This conservation, however, may be linked to resolution in t and x . In fact, to create zero probability, one requires orthogonal functions in x or t and so there is a built in resolution linked with conservation which does not appear in classical physics. In other words, for conservation of energy, one does not have infinite time resolution and one cannot say that the particle moves with a uniform distribution in time within a period. Rather, there is a resolution, \hbar/E , and within it there is the complex probability scheme $\exp(-iEt)$.

As a final note, we consider a velocity linked to the maximum resolution of x and t for free motion. This velocity is the speed of light, but it suggests that E and p are much on the same footing, i.e. that for a given E there must be a p and hence motion. We argue that if one asks: What system has energy, but requires mandatory momentum?, then one might consider a force field because p is proportional to impulse. Given that photons interact with electrons held in a electric field of the nucleus, we suggest that the photon is such a candidate.

Two Slit Interference

A constantly asked question is: Why does a quantum mechanical probability treatment of two slit interference not discern the slit through which a photon passes? A photon cannot pass through the non-slit region and it physically seems to be a point-like object, so it is not unreasonable to ask: Through which slit did it pass?

We argue, however, that in order to discern the passing through a slit, one must follow the photon in time and this requires time resolution. Classically, both x and t resolution is infinite, but in quantum mechanics it is not. Resolution is:

Space \hbar/p Time \hbar/E ((1))

If two slits are about \hbar/p apart, then the classical time associated with this distance is: $t = \hbar/(pv)$.

If one considers a photon, then:

$\hbar/pv = \hbar/E$ and so the time linked to motion across a wavelength is of the same order as the resolution period and so one cannot discern times smaller than this. It is, however, these smaller times which are needed to follow the photon through one slit of the other.

If one considers the nonrelativistic case with $E = p^2/2m$, then

$$\hbar/pv = \hbar / (mv) \quad \text{and time period} = \hbar / mv$$

Thus, nonrelativistically one cannot resolve \hbar/mv and cannot follow a particle through one slit or the other.

Relativistically:

$$\hbar/pv = t = 1 / (\gamma v) = 1 / (\gamma v/c) \quad \text{where } \gamma = 1/(1-v^2/c^2)$$

$$\text{But time resolution is: } \hbar / E = \hbar / (\gamma mc^2)$$

In this case, the time \hbar/pv is larger than \hbar/E , but the time resolution is linked to rest mass and not motion energy (as in the nonrelativistic case). Thus, it seems that one must be selective as to which energy one considers.

Conservation of Momentum and Energy

At this point, one may ask why quantum mechanics should have x and t resolution in the first place. We argue that this is due to momentum and energy conservation. These notions exist in classical physics, but need to be enforced by hand in problems. If one uses probability, then the probability should be zero for non-conserved events. The issue is that conservation of one variable requires a second variable. For example, E is measured at t_1 and must be measured again at t_2 to show that it is conserved. With p , one may use measurements in space. In both the case of E and p , $F(E_1, t)F(E_2, t) = F(E_1 + E_2, t)$ and $F_2(p_1, x)F_2(p_2, x) = F_2(p_1 + p_2, x)$, one dimension. Thus, one has a power law in E or p and may use $E t$ or $p x$. This ultimately leads to the forms $\exp(-iEt)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ which enforce energy and momentum conservation, albeit over a t or x period. This period varies with the overall E or p value which appears.

To formalize, one may associate conservation with different times. For p , one may use $-p$ and p , with the latter representing $t+dt$ and use time reversal to compare with p at x , i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx)$. For energy, $\exp(-iEt)$ where t is like a dt because it is integrated within a period, so the time reverse is $-t$. If one has $\exp(-iE_1 t)\exp(iE_2 t)$, then the period for orthogonality is: $\hbar/|E_1 - E_2|$. Thus, all of t or x is not needed to establish orthogonality, but it depends on the two E s or two p s in question.

Thus, a free particle or photon has a built-in t and x resolution and these must be taken into consideration when considering motion and interactions. One cannot use the classical viewpoint of infinite x and t resolution.

Minimal X and T Periods

Given that a particle has x and t resolution, even if one has a very precise clock and ruler, the particle exhibits $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ complex probability behaviour within the resolution periods. One may ask: What is the velocity associated with a minimum t and x resolution?, i.e.

$$x/t = (\hbar/p)(E/\hbar) = E/p \quad ((2))$$

((2)) corresponds to the speed of a photon in a vacuum. One may ask why this should be the case? Given that $(x/t)p = E$, if $p=0$, then $E=0$. In other words, in order to have energy, one must have momentum. One may ask: In which physical situation does one require E , but at the same mandatory p ? We argue that if p is considered to be proportional to impulse, then one requires energy and momentum together and that seems to fit the picture of a force field. In particular, given the manner in which light interacts with electrons in an atom, one might consider a photon as a candidate.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that due to conservation of momentum and possibly energy, quantum mechanical probability, which builds in this conservation, introduces a periodicity in t or x , i.e. a resolution. The crest-trough allows for cancellation of probability in a non-conserved scenario, but also means that a free particle has non-uniform probability within the period region, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(-iEt)$. As a result, one must take these resolutions into account and so if there is a problem which has a spatial or time length which is smaller than the intrinsic spatial or time length of a free particle or photon, one cannot resolve time and space in these regions. We suggest that this is the case for 2-slit interference and so explains why one cannot determine through which slit a photon/particle passes.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Conservation of Momentum in Terms of Probability, Space, Time (preprint, zenodo, 2024)